

Beliefs, Values and Emotions in Pharmaceutical Practitioners' Engagements with Narrow AI Adoption

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ABSTRACT

Understanding how practitioners' beliefs, values and emotions are shaping their engagement with the adoption of data mining and machine learning (narrow AI) is important to enhance knowledge about how cultural dynamics are shaping the uptake of AI across different sectors. Such knowledge can help to enhance understanding of whether and how AI ought to be integrated into specific workflows, and what the challenges, critiques and implications may be.

In this paper, we report early findings from a study exploring these issues in the pharmaceutical industry. Eighteen interviews and one focus group were completed with scientists and managers working across three projects at GSK, a multinational pharmaceutical company. Thematic analysis of the resulting data is underway, and here we report three emergent themes identified through our analysis: AI adoption in a commercial context, the desire to bring AI back down to earth, and being a non-computational scientist in the age of AI.

We conclude by arguing that the tensions that surface around AI adoption indicate that further work to mediate the relationship between AI and practitioners in a way that satisfies people in all roles is necessary.

KEYWORDS

Cultures of practice; Beliefs, values and emotions; Data cultures; Artificial Intelligence; Pharmaceutical industry

INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade the use of Data Science techniques such as data mining and machine learning - or, 'narrow AI' (DeepAI.org, n.d.) - has become more pervasive across industry and society, raising a number of challenges. Existing human-centred research about how practitioners engage in, and with the results of, these techniques tends to focus on issues such as embedding fairness, accountability, transparency, ethical and/or safety (FATES) frameworks into working practices (e.g. Constantinescu et al., 2021; Novak & Pavlicek, 2021; Stahl et al., 2022), and enhancing trust (Nazaretsky et al., 2022), acceptance (Cornelissen et al., 2022) and data literacy (Sander, 2020) among system users. This existing research tends to address these topics without paying detailed attention to the cultures of the practitioners being encouraged to engage with these emergent information practices as part of their workflow. However, theoretical and exploratory research suggests that practitioners involved in these informational activities (i.e. data scientists, system users, managers) bring to their professional practice a variety of culturally situated beliefs, values and emotions that shape their engagement with them (Bates, 2017; Bates & Elmore, 2018; Birhane et al., 2021). There is therefore a need to deepen our empirical understanding of these complex and situated cultures of practice shaping engagement with narrow AI techniques in different contexts.

In this paper, we report on research that asks: how do culturally situated beliefs, values and emotions shape data practitioners' engagements with narrow AI in different contexts of practice? The research project as a whole examines these cultures of practice across three contrasting contexts: pharmaceutical drug discovery, learning analytics in higher education, and arts practice. In this paper, we report early findings from one of these contexts – pharmaceutical drug discovery and the practice of chemoinformatics, an interdisciplinary field of information science that uses computing techniques such as data mining and machine learning to discover, for example, relationships between a chemical compound's structure and properties (Chen, 2006).

The paper begins with a brief review of the literature outlining the key debates around adoption of narrow AI in drug discovery, before introducing our theoretical approach to the study of values, beliefs and emotions. We then briefly outline our methods, prior to introducing and discussing three themes forming one of the thematic narratives emerging from our empirical work in the pharmaceutical context.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are a variety of applications of narrow AI in the pharmaceutical industry. For example, such techniques are used to extract complex and often hidden patterns from chemical datasets. They are also used to compare or further develop existing methods in order to predict undesired properties of compounds or properties associated with their absorption, distribution, and toxicity (Bender & Brown, 2018).

The current wave of excitement for applying narrow AI techniques in the drug discovery field began in the early 21st century. This has been fuelled by the rapid growth of available data and the optimisation of machine learning algorithms (Yang et al., 2019), the increase in computing power (Sellwood et al., 2018), and the development of new methods for processing data (Gasteiger, 2020). However, AI techniques in this field are not new. Prior to this wave of enthusiasm, we can also note two earlier waves in the 1960s and the 1980s (Chen, 2006). In both cases, the interest faded after a short period of excitement (Schneider, 2019).

The existing chemoinformatics literature indicate the following themes related to the culture of AI adoption in the pharmaceutical industry:

- Hype and hope around the application of narrow AI, focused largely on the promise of increased efficiency (Vamathevan et al., 2019) in the drug discovery process, but also a degree of scepticism from some in the field (Bajorath et al., 2020; Ferreira & Andricopulo, 2019).
- At points in time, there have been reports that some practitioners have been concerned about potential job losses if there was widespread adoption of AI in the field (Allen & Bannigan, 2019).
- Concerns about the black-boxed nature of some narrow AI applications, and questions about the explainability of results (Bajorath et al., 2020).
- Some have argued that novel ideas cannot be extracted from data (Hessler & Baringhaus, 2018).
- Some commentators have argued that final decisions should always be made by people (Staszak et al., 2021).

Findings from previous research and commentary within the chemoinformatics field therefore demonstrates that the application of AI techniques has provoked mixed reactions among practitioners in the drug discovery field. However, we know little about how the culturally situated values, beliefs and emotions of practitioners are shaping these engagements with these forms of ‘narrow AI’ in contexts of practice. This gap in knowledge has significance for how practitioners make sense of the adoption of AI techniques in their field, what might be influencing decision making, and ultimately how successful efforts to adopt narrow AI techniques might be in a particular context of practice.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical approach underlying the study draws on theory that recognises the intertwined nature of values, beliefs and emotions in the constitution of social phenomena, rather than approaches that theorize reason and emotion as separate binary entities (e.g. Ahmed, 2014; Bericat, 2016; Hochschild, 2012; Lloyd, 1993; Sayer, 2011; Ustek-Spilda et al., 2019). Further, drawing on work by e.g. Bates (2017) and Kitchin and Lauriault (2014), we understand the values and beliefs within a given data science context to be shaped by external social forces, including economic and political factors. In this way, our theoretical lens reflects a social constructionist, rather than a cognitive approach, to understanding values, beliefs and emotions.

We define beliefs, values and emotions as follows.

- **Beliefs** are ideas that people assert to be true. Following James (2019) and Harrison & Boyd (2018), we understand widely accepted beliefs and ideas as loose ideologies, or forms of fragmented common sense (Hall, 1987), that often contain an element of how people believe the world functions or should function. In the current literature, a number of concepts can be identified related to the author’s perception of a dominant ideology taking hold around the adoption of narrow AI and related phenomena. For example, “dataism” (van Dijck, 2014), “data-centric rationality” (Ricaurte, 2019), “data universalism” (Milan & Treré, 2019). Various counter-ideological beliefs can also be identified e.g. advocates for “complementarity” (Pasquale, 2020) and “minimum viable datafication” (Powell, 2021).
- **Values** are the beliefs that people hold and care about regarding, for example, what is right and wrong, what is important and not important (Open University, n.d.). Following Bates (2017), these values are part of what informs, frames and justifies people’s data practices. Further, following Ustek-Spilda et al (2019), we understand that organisational structures and cultural logics help develop and enact values. In the current literature, a number of values have already been identified as important to some types of technology practitioners e.g. pragmatic values such as those related to business expansion (Ustek-Spilda et al., 2019); contextual values such as moral and societal concerns (Mohamed et al., 2020); epistemic values such as generalisability, objectivity (Birhane et al., 2021; Mohamed et al., 2020); and, ‘human’ values such as liberal values, human-centric values (Pasquale, 2020).

- **Emotions.** Following work on the cultural sociology of emotions, we understand “emotions not as mere biological responses but as social feelings. These feelings are conditioned by the culture of a society (its norms, values, ideas, beliefs, etc.)” (Bericat, 2016). We recognise that data can “stir up emotions” (Kennedy & Hill, 2018), and draw on research with practitioners in other sectors that explores among other things practitioners’ feelings around the adoption of narrow AI systems in their workplaces (e.g. Eubanks, 2018).

We are applying this theoretical understanding of beliefs, values and emotion as a lens through which to guide our data collection and analysis.

METHODOLOGY

Our data collection was entirely within one organisation, GSK - a multinational pharmaceutical company. In conversation with the scientific manager who was our point of contact at the organisation, we decided to recruit participants from three projects that had integrated narrow AI techniques in their workflows. We interviewed participants in different roles: five computational chemists and biologists, four medicinal and physical chemists, two molecular biologists, six scientific managers, and one computational scientist. We interviewed the majority of people working on the three projects, this was between 5-7 per project and 18 overall. We also conducted one focus group with five people in different roles.

The interview questions and focus groups explored topics including:

- Their experience of working in the pharmaceutical industry, including their engagement with narrow AI in their work
- Their views and feelings about recent developments and priorities around narrow AI adoption in the organisation and sector
- Aspects of their work that they feel positively and negatively about, and what they feel to be important about their work
- Their engagement with colleagues about the adoption of narrow AI in the sector
- Their expectations about the future use of narrow AI in drug discovery

Data are being analysed using a combination of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), and close critical reading around key findings. We are currently in the early stages of data analysis, and here report three themes forming one of the thematic narratives identified through our analysis.

Ethical approval for the study was gained from University of Sheffield. We do not use direct quotation in the findings because our agreement with GSK requires a 30-day sign off period for use of direct quotations which was not possible to achieve in the time between call and deadline. Nonetheless, this does enable a richer narrative to be developed given the limited paper length.

EARLY FINDINGS

The following outlines three themes forming one of the thematic narratives emerging from our early findings about how data practitioners’ culturally situated beliefs, values and emotions shape their engagements with narrow AI in their work.

AI adoption in commercial context

Across the three projects that we engaged with at GSK, it was clear that the beliefs, values and emotions of practitioners about use of narrow AI techniques in the sector, and resultantly in their own work, were strongly influenced by their perceptions of what was happening externally to the organisation. As Massey (1994) theorized, we must understand ‘the global as part of what constitutes the local, the outside as part of the inside’ (p. 5).

Scientists in different roles repeatedly described a wider context in which they believed that techniques such as deep learning and AI had been overhyped over recent years, leading to large commercial investments in start-ups and research projects that promise to deliver significant pharmaceutical advances from the use of such techniques. Despite occasional positive assessments of projects such as Google Deepmind’s AlphaFold (Deepmind, n.d.), ‘Big Tech’ companies more generally were believed by some to be a key driver of this hype.

Some believed that these external factors were generating competitive pressure on managers in the sector to encourage AI adoption throughout the drug discovery pipeline, even when the techniques did not always appear to be delivering immediately on their promises. There was a perception from some that the organisation felt the promise of AI was too big a potential opportunity to miss, and that a fear of being left behind the competition was driving some important decision making

The desire to bring AI back down to earth

A number of scientists expressed frustration at this situation, perceiving claims about the potential of AI as sometimes unrealistic. Some believed this context was having a negative impact on how funders and managers were making investment decisions in the sector, and that the commercial hype was in conflict with their scientific values, which included being sceptical and engaging critically with big claims.

While scientists in all roles believed that the models could sometimes be useful and they were pleased to report that they thought the models were getting better, many of them also valued what they saw as a sense of realism about what it was possible for the techniques to deliver in the sector. Some also reflected on the uncertainty they felt around how long they might have to wait to see a more significant impact in practice, suggesting a certain amount of confidence in the techniques was required to be an advocate even in the face of sometimes disappointing results.

Being a non-computational scientist in the age of AI

Despite this degree of scientific critical thinking across different roles, there was still a sense that a belief system - or “relaxed ideology” (Harrison & Boyd, 2018) - around some of the promises of AI had taken hold in the sector in a way that, for some medicinal chemists in particular, was not necessarily realistic or desirable. Some of these chemists experienced this as feeling a pressure to conform with new practices despite holding deeply sceptical beliefs about certain types of AI applications. For some, these concerns were no longer discussed at work beyond those colleagues they knew had similar beliefs and feelings, suggesting a lack of agency some were experiencing in their work.

One of the three projects we engaged involved full automation of the workflow. The medicinal chemists on this project - despite finding AI techniques useful in other contexts - expressed concerns that on this project their non-computational contributions were less visible. They voiced frustration about there being less capacity for them to use their creativity and knowledge in this project – sometimes experiencing a sense of boredom and lack of motivation due to the change in their working practice. While not experiencing fear of losing their jobs as sometimes assumed e.g. Allen & Bannigan (2019), they were nonetheless sometimes experiencing less satisfaction with their work.

This experience contrasted with the values many practitioners held in relation to scientific work. They reflected on how it was important for them to feel that their work was enjoyable, somewhat autonomous and enabled them to use their creativity. They also valued feeling they were involved in decision making and their contributions were valued by colleagues and the organisation, and contributed to society. Yet, in practice efforts to embed AI across the drug discovery pipeline - and to build consensus in favour of this approach within and external to the organisation - had left some medicinal chemists feeling that at times these values were no longer always reflected in their experience of work, particularly on projects involving full automation of the workflow. Instead, in these cases, some were left feeling somewhat undervalued and constrained, relative to their computational colleagues who tended to feel more positive and even excited by the work.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, these three themes from our early findings begin to tell a richer story than the debates surfaced in the cheminformatics literature about how pharmaceutical industry practitioners in different roles feel about the adoption of narrow AI techniques in their workflow. Further, it situates these feelings within a broader set of beliefs and values they hold about the current hype around AI techniques, scientific practice and the experience of engaging in different types of work. The study has surfaced a variety of tensions, suggesting that further work to understand and mediate the relationship between AI technologies and practitioners in a way that satisfies scientists in all roles will be of value as we move into the next stages of our research.

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